

2022

Conference Proceedings
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International scientific and practical Conference

MODERN VIEWS AND RESEARCH

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Independent Publishing Network
Modern views and research – 2022
Chief Editor: R.Shilton

Independent Publishing Network Ltd
Mailing address – MB #1869, PO BOX 229, EGHAM, TW20
8WZ, UK
Registered Office – 71-75 Shelton Street, Covent Garden,
London, WC2H 9JQ, UK

International scientific and practical Conference
Modern views and research - 2022: Egham. Independent
Publishing Network Ltd.

Date signed for printing,

For students, research workers

ISBN 978-1-83853-487-5

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6484951>

Publisher:Independent Publishing Network.

© Authors, 2022

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Modern views and research - 2022

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Company Number 11541223

MORPHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF JAW BONE TISSUE REGENERATION DURING COMPLEX TREATMENT OF ODONTOGENIC JAW BONE CYSTS IN CHILDREN

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The lack of timely treatment of odontogenic cysts led to the development of purulent inflammation of the cyst, osteomyelitis, jaw deformity, loss of teeth, pathological fractures of the jaws, and even the development of malignant tumors of the jaws from the epithelium of the cyst wall. The experiment studied the morphological features of reparative regeneration of bone tissue in the area of the defect as a result of the treatment of odontogenic jaw cysts with A-Oss and A-Oss + PRF (platelet-rich fibrin), which led to accelerated metabolism and the formation of platelets in the defect area.

Purpose: to study the morphological features of reparative regeneration of bone tissue in the area of the defect as a result of the treatment of odontogenic jaw cysts with A-Oss and A-Oss + PRF (platelet-rich fibrin).

Materials and methods of research

Monthly rabbits of 30 chinchilla breeds were used in the experiment. All rabbits were divided into the following groups: control (n = 10) and main (n = 20). The experimental group was also divided into 2 groups: 2a-groups using osteoplastic material - A-Oss (n = 10) and 2b-groups A-Oss + PRF (platelet-rich fibrin) material

(n = 10). Animals of all groups were withdrawn from the experiment on days 7, 14, 21, 1 month and 2 months.

Xenogenic osteoplastic material - A-Oss is an osteoplastic material similar in structure to human bone tissue, made from pig bone. PRF material (platelet-rich fibrin) is platelet-rich fibrin. The material is rich in blood cells and growth factors that ensure the successful completion of the regeneration of human hard and soft tissues.

After anesthesia, a typical incision was made, turning the corner section away from the lower edge of the lower jaw of the animal. Layer upon layer followed the sharp, blunt paths to the bone, and the bone was exposed.

In the experimental area of the lower jaw, in all experimental animals, a fracture line was formed, a bone defect was formed in fissure and spherical bars when the bone was cooled with saline in the angular area (at a speed of 10,000 revolutions). Osteoplastic material in the area of the formed defect of the lower jaw of rabbits of the experimental group 2a-A-Oss; On the zone of the formed defect of the lower jaw of rabbits of the experimental group 2b, the osteoplastic material -A-Oss and the PRF material were applied, the defect area was layer-by-layer, hermetically sutured. In rabbits of the control group, the wounds were sutured in the absence of osteoplastic material in the area of the defect. On the 7th, 14th, 21st, 21st, 30th and 60th days of the postoperative period, the rabbits were taken out of the experiment.

For morphological examination, a bone fragment was cut out at a distance of 1-1.5 cm from the defect zone in the medial and distal directions. The obtained material was fixed in 10% formalin solution for 10 days, then washed with running water for 2 days. It was decalcified in a solution of nitric acid and washed with running water for several days.

In the next step, the incisions were made in ascending order in an alcohol battery for dehydration and placed in paraffin blocks, then cut with a microtome 3-5 microns thick. The sections were stained with hematoxylin-eosin stain.

Conclusion

The process of bone tissue regeneration relative to the control group in groups 2a (A-Oss) and 2b (A-Oss + PRF) in the experiment with an artificially formed defect in the bone tissue of the lower jaw occurred due to chondroid tissue, it was found that reproduction took place. The cohesive structure, hydrophilicity, surface roughness, collagen content, size and strength constancy of the A-Oss osteoplastic material accelerated the process of osteogenesis. A-Oss activated osteoblasts, allowing them to quickly attach to the surface of bone trabeculae, which accelerated the formation of concentric bone plates. It can be concluded that such properties of the A-Oss osteoplastic material made it possible to completely eliminate the defect in a short time.

The use of A-Oss in combination with the PRF material further accelerated the process of reparative regeneration. The PRF material accelerated the penetration of blood vessels through the superficial bone marrow and their growth into the bone tissue. It can be concluded that this condition led to an acceleration of metabolism in the area of the defect and the formation of lamellar bone tissue.

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